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Index

Index	3
Index of Figures	5
Index of Tables	6
Glossary	7
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction	9
2 The Project	13
2.1 Vision and Mission	13
2.2 Goals and Objectives.....	14
2.3 Governance	15
2.4 Contribution to EOSC and FAIR	16
2.4.1 Science Mesh & EOSC	16
2.4.2 Science Mesh & FAIR	17
3 Business model	17
3.1 Problem.....	20
3.1.1 Interoperability and collaboration across different sync and share services	20
3.1.2 Data sovereignty and vendor lock-in	20
3.1.3 Data reusability and FAIR principles	21
3.2 Alternative solutions	22
3.3 Customer segments	24
3.4 Early adopters	27
3.5 Value proposition.....	30
3.6 Solution	32
3.6.1 Data Science Environments	32
3.6.2 Open Data Systems.....	32
3.6.3 On-demand data transfers.....	33
3.6.4 Collaborative documents.....	34
3.7 Unfair advantage.....	37

3.8	Channels.....	37
3.9	Key metrics.....	42
3.9.1	Science Mesh Usage	42
3.9.2	Open Science	42
3.9.3	Industry Impact.....	42
4	Financial analysis.....	43
4.1	Essential operations	43
4.2	Cost structure.....	44
4.3	Funding model	44
4.3.1	Grant funding.....	44
4.3.2	Membership fees for research institutions or EFSS nodes	45
4.3.3	Service fees for researchers.....	47
4.3.4	Third-party vendor platform fees	48
4.3.5	Subsidization from commercial users and activities.....	48
4.3.6	Additional Pricing Strategies.....	49
5	Strategic Roadmap	50
6	Risk assessment	56
7	Conclusion.....	60

Index of Figures

Figure 1. Timeline of the various sources of data and stakeholder engagement on which this report is based..... 13

Figure 2. Workflow for researcher communities adopting the Science Mesh. 29

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the Science Mesh in action. (a) The overall structure, with end-users accessing their data on nodes they already use. Then, through the federated layer, end-users can collaborate with users working through different nodes. In addition, all users have access to four powerful data services. (b) An example of a CERNBox user collaborating with a Sciebo user and sharing data using the On-demand Data Transfer service. 31

Figure 4. This schematic diagram illustrates the researcher's institution paying a service provider (in this case, the Science Mesh, not an EFSS service) to provide an individual researcher with free access to the Science Mesh. Figure taken from Towards Sustainable Funding Models for the European Open Science Cloud, Financial Sustainability Task Force Progress report, November 2022. 46

Figure 5. Framework to understand the sustainability directions of the Science Mesh 51

Index of Tables

Table 1. Summary of the independent data services that the Science Mesh facilitates access to.	10
Table 2. Science Mesh Lean Canvas.....	19
Table 3. FAIR principles (adapted from go-fair.org), how they are typically employed in cloud services, and how the Science Mesh can provide a solution. Table adapted from CS3MESH4EOSC D4.3: Report on challenges and guidelines for collaborative user communities.	22
Table 4. Alternate solutions to the mesh.....	23
Table 5. Needs, wants, fears, and substitutes for the stakeholders of the Science Mesh.	25
Table 6. Market for the Science Mesh	28
Table 7. Applications enabled by the Science Mesh.....	35
Table 8. Summary of the Science Mesh channels for engagement with various customer segments.	38
Table 9. Cost for minimal operations of the Science Mesh	44
Table 10. Strategic roadmap for the Science Mesh.....	53
Table 11. Risk assessment matrix for the Science Mesh. This table was adapted from the PDES – Module C Final Report for CS3MESH4EOSC.....	57

Glossary

Acronym	Name
API	Application Programming Interface
CS3MESH4EOSC	The Science Mesh's project funded by the European Commission
CS3	Cloud Storage, Synchronization and Sharing Community
DOI	Digital object identifier
EC	European Commission
ECI	European Cloud Initiative
EFSS	Enterprise File Sync and Share
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EU	European Union
IOP	Interoperability platform
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
NRENs	National Research & Education Networks
PID	Persistent identifier
SLAs	Service Level Agreements
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh

Executive Summary

The Science Mesh aims to overcome the challenges faced by scientists in collaborating and managing large volumes of data across distributed institutes worldwide. These challenges include difficulties in coordination, reusing data that can be further exploited, and concerns about data sovereignty, security, and privacy. In its first iteration, the Science Mesh offers a seamless data platform to connect more than 600,000 users across seven countries, providing new collaborative functionalities such as Data Science Environments, Open Data Systems, On-demand Data Transfers, and Collaborative Documents.

This report presents an overview of the Science Mesh, its vision, goals, governance, and contribution to EOSC and FAIR. The lean canvas is then used to highlight the primary challenges and opportunities, including the problems being addressed by the Science Mesh, current alternatives, customer segments, early adopters, the unique value proposition, the Science Mesh solutions, unfair advantage, communication channels, key metrics, cost structure, revenue model, strategic roadmap, and risk mitigation strategies.

It is important to maintain the various Science Mesh essential operations after its current funding cycle terminates; fortunately, the Science Mesh operates leanly with minimal administrative and technical costs. The low cost of the Science Mesh essential operations is likely to be instrumental in ensuring its sustainability; however, further investments are necessary to enrol new nodes, create value for administrators and users, and enable new collaborative functionalities. Long-term revenue models are also discussed in this report to galvanize the eventual transition from governmental grant reliance.

Overall, the Science Mesh is designed to unleash collaborative research potential with its seamless data platform.

1 Introduction

The Cloud Services for Synchronization and Sharing (CS3) community is a body of providers, developers, and users of innovative storage and sync-and-share systems. The services involved are integrated with user environments and higher-level application services. The CS3 community reports on the progress in data science at all levels, namely local laboratories, regional collaborations, and global science. Applications provided by the various CS3 partners range from innovative big-data analysis to science outreach and education.

The CS3 community have seen vast deployment in recent years within the education and research domain. The success of CS3 at the national level and at the scale of individual institutions is realized with these services becoming an essential tool of the daily workflows for thousands of researchers, students, and scientists. Crucially, however, these services remain largely disconnected. CS3 development and deployment occurs mostly in isolation. This phenomenon generates major interoperability issues for the end-users, but also presents a tremendous opportunity for further maturation and expansion of the CS3 Community as a whole. Given the promising current state of CS3 as a whole and its community uptake, combining the various CS3 systems and services into a joint, coordinated service for users in research and academia would galvanize open-science on a pan-European level.

The Science Mesh, the primary asset of the CS3MESH4EOSC Project, aims to create an interoperable federation of data and higher-level services to enable friction-free collaboration between European researchers. More specifically, the Science Mesh intends to connect existing research data services through vendor-neutral Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) and protocols. The Science Mesh will bring together existing Enterprise File Sync and Share (EFSS) services that currently host approximately 600,000 user accounts across Europe and beyond; importantly, the Science Mesh prioritizes future expansion to serve additional research communities. Moreover, the Science Mesh will be a key component of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), an initiative to create a “trusted, virtual, federated environment in Europe to store, share and re-use research data across borders and scientific disciplines”.

There are three main components of the Science Mesh; firstly, to allow Science Mesh end-users (i.e., researchers) to grant data access permission to collaborators, the Science Mesh establishes a federated authentication space which delegates identification of users on existing authentication services (e.g., EduGAIN-based SSO systems), which researchers already use to establish their identity across research institutes. The communication between those isolated systems is assured by the cornerstone of the Science Mesh – the interoperability platform (IOP), which enables different EFSS services to communicate with one another. The IOP relies on a set of interoperable protocols and APIs to connect the various nodes, applications, and functionality; effectively establishing a federated layer on top of existing technology. Above the latter exists the uppermost layer of the Science Mesh, namely

a collection of data-exchanging services/applications. An important clarification needs to be made concerning the relationship between the Science Mesh federated layer and its various data services. The IOP and federated layer represent the central technology that makes the Science Mesh itself a reality, connecting the researcher to different EFSS services and providing access to several data services. On the other hand, the data services themselves represent a series of autonomous applications that are, in principle, fully operable without the Science Mesh (although at a limited capacity, that is, with no cross-node exchanges). As such, the Science Mesh and its federated layer simply enable end-users to access off-site data services (see Table 1 for summary and Section 3.6 for details).

Table 1. Summary of the independent data services that the Science Mesh facilitates access to.

Data Service Category	Description
Data Science Environments	Services allowing researchers to interactively work on algorithms and data processing programs via a web interface on a remote site. They will facilitate collaborative research and the cross-federation sharing of computational tools, algorithms, and resources.
Open Data Systems	Services responding to the need for integration of open data repositories within the Science Mesh. Ultimately, researchers will be able to organize data via tagging and metadata assignment, for instance, converting a dataset into a published and referable archive record, stored on an open data repository, archive, or library for long-term archiving. Importantly, using persistent identifiers (e.g., ORCID), researchers will be able to tag datasets with specific accessibility.
On-demand data transfers	A set of applications allowing efficient data-based collaboration, where researchers will be able utilize high-speed data transfer services from remote locations to local sites, and vice-versa. Data transfers can occur either directly between EFSS services, or via an EFSS initiation that is then offloaded to a secondary service.
Collaborative Documents	Services offering researchers collaborative editing applications in real-time with data shared in different folders, ultimately allowing a real-time, cross-federation platform for document collaboration.

Prospective users of the Science Mesh are diverse and include service providers, policy makers and citizens, software developers, and system administrators (see Section 3.3 for more detail). However, as mentioned previously, the development of the Science Mesh has been largely driven by the challenges facing individual researchers and research institutions

(i.e., fragmentation in file and application services, digital sovereignty, and the application of FAIR principles in research). Accordingly, the primary targeted end-users of the Science Mesh are individual researchers. Along with the benefits that come with addressing the three aforementioned challenges, the adoption of the Science Mesh by researchers relies largely on the ease of joining the Science Mesh and the negligible impact on researchers' workflow. Indeed, by building on top of EFSS services that researchers already use, Science Mesh adoption barriers are lowered as researchers would only have to use their institute's existing service to collaborate with external parties.

Importantly, a distinction needs to be made between Science Mesh customers and end-users. This in lieu of (a) the need to structure the Science Mesh as a sustainable, self-sufficient entity that does not permanently rely on public funds and (b) several stakeholders are in fact involved in the ultimate adoption of the Science Mesh (i.e., EFSS services, research institutions that use these EFSS services, and researchers within these research institutions). These issues, along with revenue models and customer/end-user scenarios are discussed at a later stage in this report.

In addition, an important note needs to be made on the overall "business model" of the Science Mesh. That is, the initiative is designed purely to be sustainable and does not have any intentions to pursue profit. In fact, as a consequence of the Science Mesh essentially being an interoperability and signalling interface on top of existing and well-populated services (with long service histories, established stakeholder representation, and financial resilience), the Science Mesh is itself *inherently* sustainable from the purely technical point of view. Considering that, the financial analyses presented here delve into the cost structure of the essential Science Mesh operations as well as various revenue models to ensure this sustainability.

The most pertinent challenges facing the success of the Science Mesh are first and foremost, the obvious technical challenges that accompany such an initiative (discussed in detail in additional Project Deliverables). However, the Science Mesh project consortium is poised and confident that it will deliver on its targets because of four primary reasons: (1) the consortium brings a unique understanding of the technology and a proven track record of collaboration with EU companies operating within the cloud storage space; (2) the consortium has delivered cloud storage services at large scale to data-intensive scientific domains; (3) the Science Mesh architecture operates on top of existing, established, and well-populated services; and (4) the Science Mesh can be readily integrated into a rich ecosystem of services coordinated by EOSC (e.g. EOSC Exchange). In addition, the success of the Science Mesh hinges on gaining support from two stakeholder groups, namely the research community and EFSS services. Cloud vendors upstream will need to open their service sufficiently to allow themselves to plug into the Science Mesh, ultimately allowing their service to be interoperable with other vendors. This report elaborates on the current structure of vendor involvement and the associated EFSS services that are to be incorporated into the Science

Mesh. Thirdly, the long-term sustainability of the Science Mesh relies on whether researchers will actually use the service. As mentioned previously, by building on top of EFSS services that the researchers already use, the barriers to adopting the Science Mesh should be imperceptible to them. Finally, there is the challenge of unravelling the financial sustainability for the essential operations of the Science Mesh.

Indeed, the ***business impact assessment and roadmap for effective management*** presented here, aims to elucidate on strategies for the sustainability of the Science Mesh, and to construct a roadmap for its effective management. The report is based largely on discussions with project partners and in-depth desktop research (see Figure 1 for details). More specifically, we conducted several one-on-one interviews with various project partners from different project work packages to collect their ideas on the future sustainability and management of the Science Mesh. In addition, we held three workshops with the majority of project partners present at each. The first workshop was conducted in collaboration with Horizon Results Booster¹ and took the form of an online workshop; the primary goal being to understand the key exploitable results (KERs) and the value proposition of the Science Mesh. The second was an in-person workshop held in Pisa, with the goal to understand future funding models and risks. Finally, the third was another in-person workshop held in Barcelona with the primary goal being to validate the consolidated findings. Apart from collecting data within the project consortium, we also gained several valuable insights from similar projects under the European Open Science Cloud. More specifically, we assessed the projects listed in the report *Landscape of EOSC-Related Infrastructures and Initiatives*² (pages 93 – 105) from the EOSC Executive Board Working Group (WG). For each of these projects, we explored their deliverables related to sustainability, business models, exploitation, and future roadmaps.

¹ <https://www.horizonresultsbooster.eu/>

² European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, *Landscape of EOSC-related infrastructures and initiatives : report from the EOSC executive board working group (WG) landscape*, Publications Office, 2020, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/342650>

Figure 1. Timeline of the various sources of data and Science Mesh stakeholder engagement on which this report is based.

The structure of the report is as follows; a brief overview the CS3MESH4EOSC vision, mission, and goals; an introduction into its contribution to EOSC and FAIR; and an assessment of the governance structure within the Project, including its legal form and management composition. Thereafter, readers will get to the core of this report, namely a full Science Mesh “business model” exposition, including assessments of the underlying problems creating the necessity for the Science Mesh, the different customer segments, the overall value proposition of the Science Mesh, the solutions it provides (i.e., the federated layer and the four data services), and important channels to access users and customers. This is followed by a comprehensive financial analysis, whereby the essential operations, cost structures, and potential revenue models are unpacked. We then conclude with a risk assessment and a strategic roadmap for CS3MESH4EOSC.

2 The Project

2.1 Vision and Mission

The CS3MESH4EOSC Project aims to address the challenges of the fragmentation of file and application services, digital sovereignty, and the application of FAIR principles in the everyday practice of researchers. To do so, the mission of CS3MESH4EOSC is to create an interoperable federation of higher-level services to enable friction-free collaboration between European researchers. This will be achieved by leveraging the momentum of recent cloud service provisioning and uptake in National Research & Education Networks (NRENs) and public research sectors in Europe. The CS3MESH4EOSC project will design, build, and deploy the necessary technologies to achieve this.

Initially, eight EFSS services (or ‘nodes’) are to join the Science Mesh. These eight nodes are [CERNBox](#), [CESNET](#), [Cubbit](#), [DEIC](#), PSNC, [SURF Drive](#), [SWITCHdrive](#), and [Sciebo](#) (see

cs3mesh4eosc.eu/nodes for more detail). End-users of these EFSS services will thus ultimately benefit from friction-free collaboration between them. By plugging into the Science Mesh, EFSS services will offer easy access to data across institutional and geographical boundaries.

The established infrastructure and network of EFSS services will gradually be expanded upon and offered to the entire education and research community in Europe.

CS3MESH4EOSC vision: To address the challenges of the fragmentation of file and application services, digital sovereignty, and the application of FAIR principles in the everyday practice of researchers.

CS3MESH4EOSC mission: To create an interoperable federation of higher-level services to enable friction-free collaboration between European researchers.

2.2 Goals and Objectives

The key result of the CS3MESH4EOSC Project will be the deployment of the Science Mesh – a pan-European storage and application service mesh.

The achievement of this deployment relies on 10 CS3MESH4EOSC Project objectives:

Interoperable Service Foundation:

1. **Create the software foundation for the Science Mesh service** (i.e., produce the key enabler of the service by extending and standardizing vendor-neutral APIs and protocols).
2. **Integrate the Science Mesh into the EOSC-hub catalog** (i.e., to allow Science Mesh integration with existing EOSC services. With the end of the EOSC-hub project and the start of EOSC-future, the target has now become integration into EOSC Exchange).
3. **Create an open software environment for technology providers/users of the Science Mesh to make contributions** (i.e., allowing new features and services to be integrated into the Science Mesh, with the service benefiting from contributions from all stakeholders).

Sustainability and Federated Sites

4. **Establish policies and a trusted sharing and collaboration model for the Science Mesh** (i.e., authentication, authorization, resource access, delegation, responsibilities, etc.).

5. **Define criteria and establish the measures for achieving service excellence of federated sites** (i.e., monitoring, testing, reporting, accounting, defining criteria to join the Science Mesh).
6. **Sustainably assure low and predictable costs for joining the Science Mesh.**

Application and Users

7. **Integrate high-level application services into the Science Mesh platform** (i.e., the four data service categories, namely Data Science Environments, Open Data Systems, On-demand data, and Collaborative documents).
8. **Validate the system in close connection with end-users** (i.e., researchers).

CS3 and EOSC Community

9. **Disseminate project results during project execution – providing training/networking opportunities for the CS3 community.**
10. **Deliver the impact assessment of the Science Mesh in relation to new business cases and market evolution.**

2.3 Governance

Once the Science Mesh project ends, it would be important to keep the partners engaged to maintain the infrastructure and to plan for the next steps to further its impact to the research community. To ensure this, the CS3MESH4EOSC project has already created a plan (refer to Deliverable 2.2 – “Science Mesh service operational procedures”) on the future governance of the Science Mesh. Nonetheless, to supplement this document, we describe the guiding principles on how the Science Mesh can be effectively governed.

We look at similar projects to understand how to formalize the governance of the Science Mesh. One similar project is the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure, an infrastructure enabling integrated data services and resources for research through its network of more than 25 research organisations, data, and computing centres. To support its mission, EUDAT Ltd was established as a “*not-for-profit service company and value-added reseller of data management services*”³. Furthermore, EUDAT members signed a partnership agreement, which defines the roles of different partners and the Secretariat which is “*responsible for managing, on a daily basis, the CDI Agreement and for coordinating the development and operation of the CDI infrastructure.*”

³ D2.10: EUDAT2020 Business Plan; Rob Baxter; <http://www.eudat.eu/>

Similar processes can be pursued for the Science Mesh, in the long term. However, in the short term, it would be more important to ensure the commitment of the partners to regularly meet to discuss the maintenance and future developments of the Science Mesh. It has already been agreed by the various partners to meet frequently, to ensure that the project's outputs are followed up on and sustained for further adoption.

While establishing a legal entity is a good long-term goal, this is not of high priority for the period when the funding ends. Such founding process would require coordination across the different partners and approval from authorities within their organizations, which may take a long time. As such, this can be postponed as long as the partner representatives within the Science Mesh are aligned on the future sustainability plans.

2.4 Contribution to EOSC and FAIR

The Science Mesh will contribute and be integrated to the larger EOSC initiative and the scientific community's movement towards FAIR. The CS3MESH4EOSC project has created separate deliverables focusing solely on how we will engage with EOSC (refer to Deliverable D2.5: Service included in EOSC-FUTURE). Nonetheless, we briefly describe the guiding principles through which we can contribute to EOSC and FAIR.

2.4.1 Science Mesh & EOSC

The Science Mesh project aims to be a natural vehicle to raise public awareness in Open Science in the European Union and beyond. The Science Mesh will engage with researchers by integrating with their current institutional "sync and share" service providers, enabling them to easily implement and embrace Open Science practices.

To further strengthen this strategy, the Science Mesh should be deeply integrated into EOSC and serve as a backbone to several of its initiatives. For many researchers, the Science Mesh would be their first and primary contact with the EOSC, as the Science Mesh would be already reachable through their already existing providers. The Science Mesh will engage researchers, developers, and professionals, linking these different communities and enabling them to collaborate via EOSC. Apart from researchers, the Science Mesh will also create an opportunity to further increase awareness of issues such as digital sovereignty and data privacy with service providers and industry users.

To ensure productive integration, we will be informed about other integration plans by similar projects. Many projects provide frameworks on how to integrate with EOSC. The Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges (NEANIAS) 4 and

⁴ D8.1: Novel EOSC Services for Emerging Atmosphere, Underwater & Space Challenges; EOSC integration plan; József Kovács; https://www.neanias.eu/images/neanias/Deliverables/D81_M9EOSC_Integration_Plan2020-08-12.pdf

European Open Science Cloud Photon and Neutron Data Services (EXPANDS)⁵ project provides a useful framework on how to integrate with the EOSC initiative.

The EOSC has funded many digital infrastructures and these infrastructures often operate without the knowledge of one another. The Science Mesh will perform a bridging function, integrating some of those disparate services and making them interoperable. For instance, the Science Mesh, through its Research Data Service (RDS), is already interoperable with OpenAIRE tools, allowing metadata aggregation and direct export to OpenAIRE repositories such as Zenodo. All the actors in research and collaboration workflows will also be able to interact with each other without leaving their institution's service interface.

2.4.2 Science Mesh & FAIR

The Science Mesh service will allow sites running sync and share services for their users to retain control of their datasets, while becoming FAIR compatible. The Science Mesh will directly support and encourage FAIR and GDPR compliant data practices: users of all existing participating sites will be capable of easily augmenting data stored with full, schema-compliant metadata, which can be queried cross-site. Thus, data that was previously un-reusable, will become annotated and discoverable. The Open Cloud Mesh standard will help create an underlying infrastructure upon which it would be easier to implement FAIR services to make data interoperable through the Science Mesh.

Users will have an interface at their fingertips which adds a publishing and PID minting pathway to the data lifecycle, providing the levels of discoverability that will make data properly citable and reusable. These FAIR-enhancing capabilities will be directly linked at the interface level with content creation capabilities and interactions across the federated sharing service infrastructure: collaborative documents' editing, creation of Notebooks, and results from computational environments and transferred datasets.

3 Business model

We begin our discussion of the proposed Science Mesh “business model” with a Lean Canvas (Table 2). The Lean Canvas is an adaptation of the Business Model Canvas by Alexander Osterwalder which Ash Maurya⁶ created in the Lean Startup spirit (Fast, Concise, and Effective startup). Lean focuses on problems, solutions, key metrics, and competitive advantages⁷. Ultimately, the Lean Canvas should allow an unknowing third-party to review it,

⁵ Scardaci, Diego, Salvat, Daniel, Fuhrmann, Patrick, Barty, Anton, Ashton, Alun, & Servan, Sophie. (2020). ExPaNDS General Architecture description in relation to the EOSC services. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3697704>

⁶ For more information about the Lean Canvas, refer to this blogpost: <http://www.ashmaurya.com/2012/02/why-lean-canvas/>

⁷ HRB; PDES – Module C Final Report for CS3MESH4EOSC: Interactive and agile/responsive sharing mesh of storage, data, and applications for EOSC; Tomasz Cichocki

understand the KER, the underlying problems being addressed, the customer segments, revenue models etc.

In Section 3, we use the Lean Canvas as a basis to expand from, providing a detailed breakdown of the following Science Mesh components:

- 3.1. Underlying **problems** being addressed.
- 3.2. **Alternative solutions** to end-users.
- 3.3. **Customer segments** that the Science Mesh will engage with.
- 3.4. Science Mesh **early adopters**.
- 3.5. The unique **value proposition** of the Science Mesh.
- 3.6. The **solution** that the Science Mesh provides to address the underlying problems.
- 3.7. The Science Mesh's **unfair advantage** which makes the initiative difficult to reproduce.
- 3.8. **Channels** of engagement between the Science Mesh and its customer segments.
- 3.9. **Key metrics** to be used when evaluating the current/future performance/success of the Science Mesh.

Table 2. Science Mesh Lean Canvas.

<p>PROBLEM</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interoperability and collaboration across different sync and share services - Data sovereignty and vendor lock-in - Data reusability and FAIR principles <p>ALTERNATIVE SOLUTIONS</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Commercial cloud provider status quo - Creating new environments (e.g., Amazon Web Services, SharePoint) where users can collaborate 	<p>SOLUTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Seamless data sharing across services - Collaborative functionalities (e.g., document editing, data science) across different services - Workflow for making data FAIR 	<p>UNIQUE VALUE PROPOSITION</p> <p>Unleash collaborative research potential with Science Mesh's seamless data platform.</p>	<p>UNFAIR ADVANTAGE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Service is integrated on top of existing services, enabling frictionless adoption - Relation with cloud providers - Knowhow in data storage - Relations with the scientific community. - Working within a community that already exists 	<p>CUSTOMER SEGMENTS</p> <p>Main stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Researchers - Research infrastructures, service providers and system administrators - Software developers and industry - Policy makers & citizens <p>EARLY ADOPTERS</p> <p>Scientific communities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Particle physics - Astrophysics - Digital humanities - Earth observation
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Central monitoring - Data services - Service desk 	<p>FUNDING MODELS <u>(ranked by viability)</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grant funding - Requiring validation: Membership fees (research institutions/EFSS services) - Requiring exploration: Third-party vendor platform fees <li style="padding-left: 40px;">Subsidization from commercial users and activities - Not recommended: Service fee for researchers 			
<p>Designed by: The Business Model Foundry (www.businessmodelgeneration.com/canvas). Word implementation by: Neos Chronos Limited (https://neoschronos.com). License: CC BY-SA 3.0</p>				

3.1 Problem

The Science Mesh initiative is tackling three primary challenges; namely (1) The lack of standardization and interoperability among different sync and share services has created fragmentation, hindering the ability to collaborate and exchange information. (2) Data sovereignty and vendor lock-in are major concerns for research organizations. (3) There is a need for better data management and stewardship practices to maximize the impact and value of research outputs. These challenges are expanded on below.

3.1.1 Interoperability and collaboration across different research services

A new scientific research paradigm has emerged in the last few decades, whereby researchers from diverse domains can collaborate remotely on challenging scientific problems. However, the lack of standardization and interoperability among the various institutional and cloud services they use has created fragmentation and hindered the users' ability to collaborate and exchange information freely.

Unhindered collaboration possibilities for researchers requires interoperability between the services that they use on a daily basis. Further, interoperability is crucial as it allows different systems to function and interact together, which ultimately provides end-users with improved scalability, wider resource availability, cost efficiency, and reduced energy consumption. Moreover, it can enable the creation of new services that leverage existing institutional and cloud resources, making it a possible cost-effective solution for organizations.

We believe that the ScienceMesh can constitute a viable alternative to commercial cloud services, as it leverages the collective power of smaller-scale local EFSS-based solutions, which are currently scattered around Europe and the globe. Through cross-integration, these setups can provide more complete and more useful services to their users.

3.1.2 Data sovereignty and vendor lock-in

Cloud computing has transformed the way in which research organizations store and exchange data, with certain sectors in research relying extensively on commercial computer clouds. Nevertheless, this advancement has presented its own set of problems: one of the major concerns is the security and privacy of data, as well as data sovereignty. Research organizations are uneasy about sensitive data that may be accessed or compromised by unauthorized parties. Indeed, data security and privacy issues are less pronounced among the research organisations targeted by the Science Mesh, given their somewhat “private” nature. However, this beneficial position can change rapidly against the backdrop of possibly inadequate computing capacity or services, along with the lure of commercial solutions.

In addition, there is the necessity to ensure that they have control over their data and that it is stored in compliance with relevant laws and regulations. This is compounded by the fact that there is a growing demand for data to be made openly accessible for reuse by other researchers, while also maintaining privacy and security standards.

Secondly, research organizations are also wary of vendor lock-in, where they become dependent on a single cloud provider for a specific service. This issue is very much related to the challenge of interoperability. A lack of interoperability creates downstream challenges for end-users, with the often-high costs of switching from one provider to another leading to vendor lock-in. Organizations may have financial limitations and outstanding contracts with providers that make it difficult to switch to alternative EFSS services.

Ultimately, data sovereignty and vendor lock-in can have substantial impacts on EFSS service end-users. Accordingly, the Science Mesh architecture is designed to significantly attenuate these two wide-ranging challenges.

3.1.3 Data reusability and FAIR principles

The exponential increase in the amount of data produced by the scientific community in the past decade has led to the demand for better data management and stewardship practices. To help scientists leverage this data, FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) data principles have been called for. Essentially, **findable** data must have appropriate metadata and be indexed, **accessible** data requires effective authorizations, **interoperable** data can be used across different environments, and **reusable** data is well-described and can be replicated for other uses.

Ultimately, applying FAIR principles helps maximize the impact and value of research outputs. Moreover, not applying these principles in everyday research practices is problematic for several overlapping reasons. It can result in a lack of discoverability of research outputs, hinder the reuse of data and other research outputs (thus limiting its impact and usefulness), and yet again, it can lead to a lack of interoperability between different datasets and systems. FAIR data principles help reduce inefficiencies in the scientific process, such as wasted time and extra costs, including double funding, storage, and licensing. In fact, the lack of FAIR data has been estimated to cost the EU approximately EUR 10.2 billion per year (European Commission 2019). Beyond reducing inefficiencies, FAIR data promises to open new frontiers in human knowledge. Most notably, by making data FAIR, researchers can reuse data and find other applications for it previously unforeseen by the original researchers who first collected it. Moreover, FAIR enables international collaborations, bringing together teams with different specializations to collaborate on specific scientific problems.

The design of the Science Mesh will address several challenges related to incorporating FAIR principles into the workflows of researchers (see Table 3 for details).

Table 3. FAIR principles (adapted from go-fair.org), how they are typically employed in cloud services, and how the Science Mesh can provide a solution. Table adapted from CS3MESH4EOSC D4.3: Report on challenges and guidelines for collaborative user communities.

FAIR Principle	Description	Current setting	Science Mesh solution
Findable	Metadata and data are easy to find for both humans and computers.	Data may not be properly labelled for easy search.	Data can be easily labelled thanks to specialized applications offered as part of the Science Mesh environment.
Accessible	Once data is found, they can be accessed with authorisation and authentication.	Data may be stored in silos that are difficult to access.	Data can be accessed through existing robust authentication systems which are federated through the ScienceMesh.
Interoperable	Data can be readily used by applications for analysis, storage, and processing.	Data and apps to open them may only work in their original platform.	Data and apps can be used across systems through an interoperability layer. Community data formats employed whenever possible.
Reusable	Metadata and data are well-described for replication and integration.	Data is stored or archived without thinking about reusability.	Tools are deployed to integrate reusability in the workflow. Integration with data repositories.

3.2 Alternative solutions

The main competitor for the Science Mesh is just the status quo of sticking with commercial cloud providers such as Google drive, Dropbox, and Microsoft. All these different services enable users to store and share their files. While this can be convenient, the problem is when file sharing is needed for users from different institutes with different services. Either, users have to share a link, and thus, make collaboration possible but not secure. Or, other users can be forced to sign up and create an account with the provider in question. In either case, sharing files is filled with friction.

Bigger challenges occur when researchers try to collaborate. Microsoft, for example, offers a collaborative editing tool with SharePoint – a web-based collaborative platform that integrates natively with Microsoft Office. While this indeed represents a viable alternative to the Science Mesh Collaborative documents service, the data privacy concerns surrounding platforms such as these should ultimately make the Science Mesh offering more appealing. In addition to this, alternative solutions such as the commercial cloud providers mentioned above are highly prone to vendor lock-in. As end-users become accustomed to their cloud solution, the relative effort of migrating their data and workflows to alternative solutions increases dramatically. This in turn makes it easy for cloud vendors to increase their prices without a high risk of losing users. We summarize these solutions in Table 4.

Table 4. Alternate solutions to the mesh.

Alternate solution	Strength	Weakness	Science Mesh response
To store and share files: opt for public cloud storage services such as DropBox, Google Drive, and OneDrive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Convenience - Highly curated user experience - Users are already used to it - Ease to migrate data when changing institutions (when stored in personal cloud) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Privacy and security concerns - Vendor lock-in - Difficulty in ensuring access to only authorized collaborators - Not catered to specific research needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Emphasize importance of Open Science and data sharing - A system with digital sovereignty at its core – all data is managed by its owners - Emphasize ease in data sharing - Rely on existing open-source sync and share solutions (e.g., ownCloud, Nextcloud) with recognizable interfaces
To store and share files: use an institutional cloud service without the Science Mesh	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Users already are familiar with these services - Data privacy and security - Integration with institution's computing services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Barriers to data sharing (e.g., researchers would have to exchange technical details such as passwords and identifiers to share information) - Researchers cannot easily carry their data with them when changing institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Make it easy to use the Science Mesh from the institutional cloud service - Minimize clicks to navigate interface
To collaborate: use specific cloud applications such as Google Docs, Office365	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Convenience - Highly curated user experience - Users are already used to it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Privacy and security concerns - Difficulty in ensuring access to only authorized collaborators 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Preserve digital sovereignty - Provide recognizable interfaces by relying on existing open-source software and integrating it within the mesh (e.g., CodiMD)
To collaborate: join project-based or domain-based clouds built on services like AWS, Azure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For computationally intensive applications, researchers are already used to these interfaces - Convenience and scalability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - May add to the fragmentation of the cloud ecosystem - Learning curve - Subject to vendor lock-in 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide a rich suite of applications which rely on the Science Mesh and interface with research-empowering systems (e.g., Rucio)

3.3 Customer segments

The primary beneficiaries of the Science Mesh would be researchers who are a part of research organizations. These research organizations, in turn, have IT departments that aim to provide cloud services to various users. For the Science Mesh to be successful, it must address the needs, wants, fears, and substitutes related to these two main parties. We describe how the Science Mesh addresses each of these through its benefits, experience afforded, trust levers, and risk mitigation schemes (Table 5).

Beyond these primary beneficiaries, as a public infrastructure, the project should also address the concerns of other stakeholders. In the case of the Science Mesh, the secondary beneficiaries are industry (commercial users and software developers) and policymakers – stakeholders which we also included in the analysis.

Table 5. Needs, wants, fears, and substitutes for the stakeholders of the Science Mesh.

Primary beneficiaries		Other stakeholders		
Researchers	Science Mesh	Service Providers and Research Organizations	Commercial users / Software developers	Policymakers
Needs -To be able to focus on their research -To manage their data conveniently through reliable services - To find, access and use relevant research data - Ability to collaborate seamlessly with other users -Ensure that they follow guidelines and regulations with respect to data	--->Benefits<--- - Built on top of existing platforms that researchers are already familiar with - Integrates various data management tools that enable researchers to collaborate and share data - Enable researchers to comply with data management requirements	Needs - Minimize the inefficiencies in the research process - Make data management tools and services available to researchers - Comply with regulations with respect to data - Manage costs and maintain flexibility in selecting service providers	Needs -To be able to focus on product development -To manage their data efficiently - To have their products have wider reach	Needs - Produce impact from science - Promote Open Science and FAIR data
Wants - Data management tools that are easy to use with low learning curve - Additional convenience in sharing data to collaborators and in trusted repositories - Training and Help desk	--->Experience<--- - Plug in to existing services - Convenience In pursuing FAIR data - Reduce clicks and complexity for various operations - Have a training program - Helpdesk	Wants - Provide high quality service to researchers - Ensure high visibility to researchers - Maximize the impact of research - Connect better with industry - Provide training	Wants - Training and Help desk - Access to newest tools	Wants - Demonstrate impact of Open Science initiatives
Fears - Wasting time to learn new data management practices - Bureaucracy - Additional costs	--->Trust levers<--- - Low effort / requirements needed to use the Science Mesh - Integration with EOSC - Constant feedback from users	Fears - Lack of manpower to serve users - New developments require substantial investment in technologies or additional costs	Fears - Potential security and privacy breaches - Wasting time to learn new data management practices	Fears - Lack of quantifiable impact from Open Science investments

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Potential security and privacy breaches - Losing files 		<p>to operate</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additional complexity from pursuing EOSC - Justifying investment in data storage & resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bureaucracy - Additional costs - Losing files 	
<p>Substitutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using consumer cloud storage services such as Google Drive, Dropbox 	<p>--->Mitigation<---</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engagement with communities to respond to their specific needs 	<p>Substitutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using public cloud storage services such as Google Drive, Dropbox 	<p>Substitutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using public cloud storage services such as Google Drive, Dropbox 	<p>Substitutes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Status quo

The Science Mesh's primary beneficiaries are researchers, especially those coming from universities and research institutes. By being part of one of the Science Mesh nodes, researchers will gain access to a global collaboration platform, seamlessly integrated in their current working environments. Collaboration with users and groups at other institutions will be just one click away and readily accessible. FAIR-abiding data archiving, sharing and publication will be available to all these researchers. As will cross-institutional collaboration on sharing documents, enabling researchers to work, both independently and jointly, by using their domestic data without the need to register on an additional external EFS platform. We consider that end-users and research communities will be involved in the long-term with a high level of communication activities, also after the end of the project as they constitute our target user base for the success of Science Mesh to be used at European level and beyond.

These researchers are part of larger organizations that the Science Mesh would also have to benefit. Key to the success of the Science Mesh is serving and providing value to universities and research organizations. Particularly, we focus on the groups within these institutes that handle IT policy and governance. With the Science Mesh, they will gain the freedom to choose their storage and application providers without compromising on functionality and without the risk of creating disconnected service silos for their users. Service managers and site administrators will gain a streamlined and well documented environment for stable service operation at scale. They will benefit from the cumulated knowledge, operational experience, and support of a large community.

Apart from academia, parties from the industry would also benefit from the Science Mesh. Researchers from industry can plug in to the Science Mesh to easily collaborate with their colleagues from academia. More importantly, we also see the Science Mesh as a platform that can enable the tech Industry in Europe and beyond to extend their current user base and ensure integration with the growing and evolving service ecosystem of the European Open Science Cloud. Software developers contribute to the integration of new application services, access new software applications not available on the market and will be allowed to sell this service to their target user communities. The involvement of commercial software developers is crucial for the complete deployment of the Science Mesh at European and global level.

Finally, governments and NGOs have interest in promoting Open Science and FAIR data. The Science Mesh would support these, enabling digital sovereignty in policy making processes and effectively increasing both open access and human capital. The Science Mesh would be a crucial part of the European Open Science Cloud, which has been a grand initiative by the EU.

3.4 Early adopters

In the following table, we explore the size of the potential beneficiaries of the Science Mesh in terms of the number of users and nodes (Table 6).

Table 6. Market for the Science Mesh

	Number of users	Number of nodes (research institutes / service providers)
Total Addressable Market How big is the total market	2 M researchers in Europe	100 NRENs and Research infrastructures
Serviceable obtainable market How big is the market that can be reached with current resources	600,000 researchers are under the CS3 community	16 nodes responded in the latest CS3 survey
Early adopters*	Research: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RNP (Brazilian NREN) - SUNET (Swedish NREN) - HIFIS (Helmholtz Federated IT Services) - ESCAPE (European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures) - LOFAR (Low-Frequency Array) - RISE SMA - ETH Zurich - ENVRI-FAIR - SSHOC - OSS (Observatoire du Sahara et du Sahel) - PIONIER - Brookhaven Open Science: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EGI - Center for Open Science - EUDAT - EOSC - OCRE Open Source <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - RCLONE - ONLYOFFICE - Describo and RO-Crate - JupyterLab - Voilà 	8 partners from the Science Mesh - CERNBox, CESNET, Cubbit, DTU DEIC, PSNC, SURFDrive, SWITCHdrive, and Sciebo

*Note that the Science Mesh is still under development and not yet open to the public; as such, these simply represent communities that have expressed their interest in joining/utilizing the Science Mesh.

From the users' perspective, there are several pilot communities already involved in the planning process of Science Mesh. These are for example the high energy groups at CERN, LOFAR in the Netherlands, the RISE SMA project, and the earth observation project. Their users will be asked first for their feedback when the service goes into production (for more detail, refer to Deliverable 5.3 – “Final report on dissemination and exploitation of project results”).

From the side of the service providers, we find more than 100 NRENs serving different countries (e.g., Surf in the Netherlands) and research infrastructures serving specific communities (e.g., CERNBox in particle physics). These service providers can join the Science Mesh through an easy enrolment process. Nonetheless, we will pilot the Science Mesh through the partners in the CS3 community. These early adopters would be able to use their existing storage EFSS platforms and add the interoperability functionality.

Note that many researchers would be “homeless” in that they do not belong to these NRENs and RIs that can easily plug in to the mesh. These users would be more difficult to reach but the Science Mesh should find a way for them to be part of the ecosystem by for instance being adopted by services like EUDAT.

To maximize the impact of these engagements, it is crucial to use the outcomes to further improve the Science Mesh for its users and the providers of these users. We provide the workflow in Figure 2. Workflow for researcher communities adopting the Science Mesh.**Error! Reference source not found.2.**

Figure 2. Workflow for researcher communities adopting the Science Mesh.

3.5 Value proposition

Unleash collaborative research potential with Science Mesh's seamless data platform.

The Science Mesh is a game-changing solution for European researchers, providing a friction-free platform for collaboration that connects existing research data services through vendor-neutral APIs and protocols. An inevitable key component of the EOSC initiative, the Science Mesh enables seamless data access and transfer across borders and scientific disciplines. With its three main components, namely its identity federation, an IOP, and a collection of data services, the Science Mesh is designed to meet the needs of individual researchers and research institutions by addressing the challenges of fragmentation in file and application services, digital sovereignty, and the application of FAIR principles. In its current formulation, the Science Mesh offers access to a suite of data services, including Data Science Environments, Open Data Systems, On-demand Data Transfers, and Collaborative Documents, enabling researchers to work together seamlessly regardless of their location. This ecosystem of services will grow over time, providing even more solutions to researchers using the Science Mesh. With ease of adoption and minimal impact on researchers' workflow, the Science Mesh is the ultimate solution for researchers seeking to unlock the full potential of collaborative research.

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of the Science Mesh in action. **(a)** The overall structure, with end-users accessing their data on nodes they already use. Then, through the federated layer, end-users can collaborate with users working through different nodes. In addition, all users have access to four powerful data services. **(b)** An example of a CERNBox user collaborating with a Sciebo user and sharing data using the On-demand Data Transfer service.

3.6 Solution

The core solution put forward by the Science Mesh is its interoperable platform that builds on top of existing services. The Science Mesh aims to make it easier for researchers to store their data and share them easily with other researchers. Through this, the project enables 4 workflows:

- Data science environments
- Open data systems
- On-demand data transfers
- Collaborative documents

We describe in-depth each of these new use cases in the following section.

3.6.1 Data Science Environments

Computational notebooks have become the “de facto” platform used by researchers to interactively analyse their data and document their work. While they are now ubiquitous, limitations still exist with regards to their collaborative capabilities. The Project developed extensions for computational notebooks to enable collaborative data science. The computational notebooks are integrated into the Science Mesh. Thanks to the Science Mesh, users will be able to access remote execution environments to replay (and modify) analysis algorithms without a need to set up upfront accounts in the remote system. This will be accessible via the web interface at the remote sites of researchers, to enable them to work on algorithms and data processing programs interactively.

The functional integration with EFSS of such notebooks allows for their features to be augmented in very interesting ways. One JupyterLab plugin developed by the Project⁸ allows users to share their notebooks across the Mesh⁹, allowing collaboration to happen not only between users but also across institutional barriers. In the future, computational resources (such as BigData Spark, HPC, batch and Grid clusters) could be shared through a similar mechanism.

3.6.2 Open Data Systems

Research groups put out increasing amounts of data that can be better structured; however, many of them lack the tools to tackle this challenge. Policy makers have been increasing the pressure (the “stick”) to make data FAIR but haven’t typically offered better tooling (“the carrot”). Training up researchers to use complex tooling is a hard sell – turnover

⁸ <https://github.com/sciencemesh/cs3api4lab>

⁹ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1210538/contributions/5317088/>

is high and there is little time to devote to data structuring. A good-enough solution could help start the flywheel. Science Mesh delivers a graphical user interface that end users can use, allowing them to select files from their cloud storage, select the correct metadata schema for their discipline, annotate the files according to the schema, bundle them, and deposit them into repositories/archives/publishers, all with as much streamlining, step-through wizards and automatic harvesting/prepopulation of data as we can manage. The EFSS system user's home service account will be associated with a persistent identifier (such as ORCID) and this identity will follow the data when publishing to open data repositories. Users are able to tag datasets as public and make them public and searchable on the home service. They are also able to perform collections-level (transcending the bare file level) manipulation on data assets held in an EFSS system. Adding this feature allows users to retain metadata (produced by, e.g., instruments) as they ingest their files into the Science Mesh, and later on to connect their data collections to 3rd party systems (e.g., archives) enriched by metadata.

The tool is based on ScieboRDS¹⁰ and is aimed at beginner to intermediate users and disciplines; not replacing dedicated metadata-aware research portals that handle domain-specific data very adequately already. This would help in the move towards FAIRification, an activity currently pursued by academia and policy makers in academia. However, currently, the marketplace is fairly sparse, and what is available often has a DIY aspect to it – either only applicable to a small research discipline, or too ambitious and subsequently abandoned. FAIR on the Science Mesh has the potential to reach sufficient scale that we can exploit the tools economically. The selling point, from that point, isn't the FAIRification tools per se but the added usefulness they lend to on-prem sync & share solutions vs. less research-specific commercial cloud tools (e.g., Dropbox).

3.6.3 On-demand data transfers

Over the years, sync and share services have developed from simple data sharing services to tools of scientific research. Starting at first with relatively small data usually in the form of documents becoming scientific data sets later on. For the latter, data locality is important. Data can be shared but if that data is large in volume and must be processed multiple times, it is good that it is located nearby the computing facilities. Science Mesh provides high-speed transfer of information from remote locations to local sites across different countries, specifically supporting use-cases not able to extend processing capabilities to remote sites. It further allows for efficient data-based collaboration on on-demand basis – opposite to 'a priori' planned data processing workflows.

We are developing two methods of data transfers: so-called ad-hoc transfers involving the long tail users residing on different sync and share systems that want to copy data to each

¹⁰ <https://www.research-data-services.org/>

other; in addition, we also cater for the larger scientific collaborations that have managed data transfers and have the tooling for that and that want to integrate sync-and-share into their workflows. Sync-and-share systems will interface with their data transfer tooling. This solution will be an installable version that can run on any EFSS site. This particularly holds for the ad-hoc data transfer mechanism that targets a general audience. The managed data transfer mechanism is restricted to scientific communities having a lot of data and access to data transfer tooling as well as storage systems and EFSS' that use a federated identity mechanism for authentication and authorization.

Users will be able to initiate and handle transfers directly between EFSS services, and also transfers initiated by EFSS (Enterprise File Sync and Share) service but offloaded to a secondary service. The functionality developed will be integrated into the end-user interfaces (such as the EFSS web interface) and also available via CS3APIs to build CLI tools.

3.6.4 Collaborative documents

A common use case for users is to be able to edit documents of different types simultaneously – these can be office-like files as well as plain Markdown documents, or simple (vector-)graphics. Regular desktop editors do not offer the possibility to synchronize the input even if the file resides in a share of a sync and share service. This set of use cases targets the integration of collaborative content editing applications in the Science Mesh service, to enable cross-federation collaboration on content in real-time. Users are able to simultaneously edit documents, comment, assess versioning etc. Whenever possible, existing connectors were used for this work (for example, some of the work which had already been prototyped at CERN). Programs would be accessible to users to allow them to edit different file types that might not even be installed on their device.

For each of these four applications, we summarize their promise to the users in Table 7.

Table 7. Applications enabled by the Science Mesh

	Science Mesh interoperable Federated layer	Primary applications		Secondary applications	
		Data Science Environments	Open Data Systems	On-demand data transfers	Collaborative documents
Priority for Exploitation	Very high	Very high	Very high	Moderate	Moderate
Rationale for exploitation (UVP)	High need for digital infrastructure helping Open Science, with current alternatives not sufficient.	Collaborative data science environments are very high demand, but the options out there are still limited.	FAIR data is very much demanded by policymakers and research organizations but tools to make FAIR data are still not well developed.	Transfers of large files are needed by research groups, but current approaches are not user friendly.	Collaborative editing is always in demand, but users still prefer existing options that are more convenient.
Technology Readiness Level	6 - Technology demonstrated in a relevant environment	4 - Technology validated in laboratory environment	5 - Technology validated in relevant environment	4 - Technology validated in laboratory environment	4 - Technology validated in laboratory environment
Problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of interoperability and collaboration across cloud providers - Issues in data sovereignty and vendor lock-in - Problems with data reusability and FAIR principles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Difficulty in analysing data collaboratively - Analysing large volumes of data - Data privacy and security issues - Difficulty coordinating across geographically distributed researchers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pressure to make data FAIR, but it is time-consuming - Data is stored not to be reused again after a project ends - Lack of tools for FAIRification 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Increasing size of data generated - Transferring data across sites is inconvenient. - Challenges analysing data in remote sites 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No guarantees of security and privacy in online documents
Alternative solution /	Public cloud storage	Base JupyterLab without	FAIR is typically just ignored or	Manual	Non-GDPR-compliant

competitors	providers like OneDrive, Google Drive, Dropbox and cloud services like AWS, Azure.	collaborative capabilities.	thought as a last-minute duty.	transfer of files between sites.	services or manually syncing files.
Solution	Interoperable platform that builds on top of existing services.	A free, open-source, interactive web tool where users can combine software code, computational output, explanatory text, and multimedia resources in a single document.	A graphical user interface that allows end users to select files from their cloud storage, select the correct metadata schema for their discipline, annotate the files, bundle them, and deposit them into repositories/archives/publishers.	User friendly interface to easily copy data across sites.	Collaborative document editors that combine data privacy with user-friendly features.
Technologies used	OCM	JupyterLab, QuantStack Voilà	DESCRIBO and RO-CRATE, InvenioRDM, ScieboRDS	Rclone, FTS Rucio	Collabora, OnlyOffice, CodiMD
Beneficiaries	Researchers Service providers Research organizations Industry users	Researchers	Researchers Data librarians Policy makers	Researchers IT managers	Researchers, IT managers, Administrative personnel
Use cases		Earth Observation High Energy Physics	Digital humanities and small-instrument bioinformatics	Astronomy	Researchers and personnel at partner sites, social sciences
Adoption strategy	- Installation across participating nodes - Publication of success stories	- Installation across participating nodes - Need to train users on the collaborative functionalities	- Installation across participating nodes - Need to train users on the collaborative functionalities	- Installation across participating nodes	- Installation across participating nodes
Partner in charge	CERN	Ailleron / SoftwareMind	WWU	SURF	CERN
Status	Pre-production	Proof of Concept	Production (WWU and SUNet)	Proof of Concept	Production (CERN and WWU)

3.7 Unfair advantage

The Science Mesh provides a radical approach to solving the challenges of interoperability, data sovereignty and reusability. The Science Mesh is best positioned to answer this due to three main components: the technology design, the partners' knowhow in data storage, and the partners' embeddedness in the scientific community.

First, previous solutions have mostly focused on creating new applications, workflows, and deployments instead of working with current existing services. The Science Mesh is different in that it is integrated on top of services that thousands of users are already using. Thus, instead of adding to fragmentation, it aims to help towards consolidation through interoperability across a heterogeneous landscape.

Second, the partners in the projects are very active in the cloud storage space. They have strong connections with (or are some of them) NRENs and research infrastructures providing storage services to various researchers. Moreover, they are in constant communication with the major open-source cloud software vendors and actively collaborate with them through different channels. The commitment of the latter is important in creating a truly interoperable self-sustainable ecosystem.

Finally, they are highly embedded in the scientific community, in areas as diverse as particle physics, earth observation, astronomy, or digital humanities. By having this close connection with the actual users, the team can gain feedback quickly towards iteratively improving the Science Mesh.

3.8 Channels

Herewith we detail how the Science Mesh intends to engage with its various customer segments and how it will deliver its value proposition. The channels detailed below represent the touch points between the Science Mesh and its end-users and customers.

Table 8. Summary of the Science Mesh channels for engagement with various customer segments.

Channel Element	Description of Channel	Customer Segment Targeted by this Channel
Project website	The CS3MESH4EOSC project website serves as a platform to share information about the project, including its objectives and status, news, and contact opportunities. The website also functions as a repository for various project-related material.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators
sciencemesh.io	The sciencemesh.io site serves as one of the main products of the CS3MESH4EOSC Project that will live on beyond the cessation of the Project itself. The site serves as a one-stop location for both current and prospective users of the Science Mesh. Here, documentation on joining the Science Mesh is found, along with various other tools, including <i>Science Mesh live</i> , access to the Github community, etc.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators
Newsletters	The CS3MESH4EOSC project produces newsletters every four months, to share information about project activities, results, tools, services, news, and events. The newsletters are distributed via email and published on the project website. Interested parties can subscribe to the newsletter through the project website, and partners and participating scientific communities are regularly added to the recipient list.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators
Blogs and social media	The CS3MESH4EOSC project uses popular social media platforms like LinkedIn, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube to disseminate project results. An interactive blog exists, to facilitate the exchange of best practices and experiences related to early adopters of the Science Mesh, allowing project partners and the wider scientific audience to interact and share new ideas and requirements for services. Blog entries consist of interviews, short opinions, executive summaries of relevant deliverables, and summary reports from conferences and workshops.	Researchers, Software developers

<p>Conferences, third-party events, workshops</p>	<p>The CS3MESH4EOSC project uses several events (incl. conferences, third-party events, workshops, and webinars) as platforms for dissemination.</p> <p>One particularly noteworthy event is the CS3MESH4EOSC project final public event, taking place at the end of the project. All partners and key stakeholders from scientific communities, e-Infrastructure providers, storage/EFSS vendors, and commercial service providers are encouraged to participate.</p> <p>Throughout the duration of the project, CS3MESH4EOSC project partners have been speaking at various scientific conferences and workshops related to eScience, e-Infrastructures, Open Science, and Open Collaboration, to showcase the Science Mesh's capabilities and underlying standards and protocols.</p> <p>Finally, common information materials (e.g., leaflets, brochures, etc.) are disseminated at these events. For example, at the final public event, a purpose-designed brochure aimed at potential target groups, beneficiaries, and other stakeholders involved in the Communication Plan is to be disseminated.</p>	<p>Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators</p>
<p>Gitter community</p>	<p>Gitter, an open-source instant messaging service hosts a public chat room titled 'sciencemesh/community'. This channel allows developers to join in on discussions surrounding new research-orientated applications, while researchers can access the community to ask questions, give feedback, and stimulate further development of the Science Mesh.</p>	<p>Software developers, Researchers</p>
<p>Github contributions</p>	<p>Software developers can view and contribute the Science Mesh Code Base hosted on Github.</p>	<p>Software developers</p>
<p>Technical documentation for joining the Science Mesh</p>	<p>Extensive documentation intended for an administrator of an EFSS service wishing to join the Science Mesh. It serves as a checklist of all steps necessary to perform the task,</p>	<p>Service providers</p>

	referring to specific technical how-tos. This documentation can be obtained at https://developer.sciencemesh.io/	
<i>Science Mesh live</i>	Individuals can use Grafana to explore live Science Mesh metrics (e.g., user distribution by country and site location) in a visually appealing platform.	Service providers, Researchers
ZENODO Library	The CS3MESH4EOSC project uploads training materials, presentations, public project deliverables, and other important documentation that concerns all customer segments on the Zenodo Library. Zenodo is multi-disciplinary open repository that is maintained by CERN. All files are automatically allocated a DOI and can be located using the Zenodo search engine.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators
Podcasts, videos, and webinars	The CS3MESH4EOSC project discusses various topics that are of interest to specific customer segments via a podcast series. For example, the second podcast, entitled “ <i>Data Science Environment, what is it and what are the main benefits?</i> ”, was of particular interest to research institutions and individual researchers. Moreover, videos and webinars of Science Mesh project partner presentations and demos at events are created and disseminated to various stakeholders via several platforms.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators
Magazine articles	The CS3MESH4EOSC project also engages with various customer segments via intermittent magazine articles. For example, the Science Mesh featured in CONNECT42 ¹¹ (Page 26) – the latest issue of the GÉANT CONNECT Magazine. Herein, the Science Mesh offering was summarized, and its unique value proposition presented.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens
Press releases	Press releases are one of the primary formats for the communication of official statements or announcements directed for public release.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and

¹¹ <https://connect.geant.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/CONNECT42-A-new-era-for-digital-innovation.pdf>

		Citizens, System administrators
Outreach	The CS3MESH4EOSC project outreach activities target universities, research disciplines, and e-Infrastructure providers to create awareness among researchers, policy makers, and providers. At selected science disciplines, ESFRI facilities, and relevant H2020 projects (e.g., AARC2, FREYA, and RDA), the project also presents research results, gathers feedback and requirements, and showcases how a federated mesh of cloud services contributes to international collaborations. The project also develops educational activities for research schools to familiarize early career researchers with the Science Mesh's capabilities and explores synergies with other H2020 projects such as Up2University.	Service providers, Policy makers and citizens, Researchers
Service Desk	The CS3MESH4EOSC project intends to formulate a service desk that will be incorporated into its essential operations and used as a primary contact point for all technical matters. The service desk will be available to all customer segments that are in one way, or another, connected to the Science Mesh in a technical manner.	Service Providers, Researchers, Software developers, Policy makers and Citizens, System administrators

3.9 Key metrics

The key metrics used to assess the deployment, progress, and overall success of the Science Mesh Project can be subdivided into three separate categories, namely Usage-, Open Science-, and Industry Impact-related metrics.

3.9.1 Science Mesh Usage

- Number of end-users – the CS3 community represents a market of 600.000¹² users, which could be expanded to more than 1 million with the onboarding of other NRENs and federations.
- Number of nodes – 11 sites are currently being onboarded into the testbed¹³, with 5 of them already in pre-production state at the time of writing. The CS3 community counts on 10 other member sites which would be obvious candidates in a first phase. The current architecture could easily scale up to several dozens of nodes.
- Number of file transfers – to be closely monitored once the file transfer service is in production.
- Number and size of datasets deposited through Science Mesh pathways – the data publishing service has only recently been put in production and is now being used by its first set of researchers. This number will be closely monitored.

3.9.2 Open Science

- Number of minted persistent identifiers (PIDs).
- Number of analysis notebooks shared between users.
- Number of collaborating institutions.

3.9.3 Industry Impact

- Number of third-party developers that contribute new applications.
- Number of third-party developed applications.

¹² <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1210538/contributions/5242114/>

¹³ <https://indico.cern.ch/event/1210538/contributions/5242149/>

- Number of spin-offs developed through the Science Mesh.

4 Financial analysis

After the European Project phase reaches its end (June 2023), the Science Mesh will have to operate in the absence of external funding. This was expected and from a technical point of view, the Project has been designed from the beginning with sustainability in mind. It is then crucial to understand what the essential activities of the Science Mesh are. In this section, we estimate these immediate costs. Beyond the short-term, we also investigate potential revenue models for the future Science Mesh.

4.1 Essential operations

The Science Mesh was designed to operate with minimal costs. Unlike other services that require large data hosting expenses that also scale with the number of users, the Science Mesh is run on top of existing services which have institutional backing. By leveraging this federated approach, the Science Mesh manages to add great value to some of the tools which are used by researchers, at a negligible cost. Nonetheless, like any other service, the ScienceMesh cannot efficiently run without the work of a lean team performing administrative functions as well as technical work.

The steering group, composed of representatives from each partner, should meet regularly (2-hour call every month) to discuss the strategic pathways for the Science Mesh. Constant coordination is needed to address emerging challenges with respect to the Science Mesh, respond to user needs, integrate with EOSC, engage with cloud suppliers to name a few. The work of the steering group is implemented by the executive board, leading the various operations of the Science Mesh. Overall, the Science Mesh was designed to run very lean and efficiently with minimal administrative costs.

The technical staff would be crucial to the Science Mesh's operations. DevOps would take charge of deployment, system administration, software updates and troubleshooting. Another team in software maintenance would ensure that the codebase for the Science Mesh is kept up to date, addressing changes in the cloud services' policies. Moreover, we need to have a helpdesk to respond to questions that representatives from the nodes would have. Note that the helpdesk will not respond to users' questions as users should be able to direct their issues to the administrators of their nodes. The helpdesk's responsibility then is to help administrators connect their nodes to the Science Mesh, assign tickets, facilitate communication between nodes and assist onboarding. Overall, these technical costs are also expected to be very minimal.

4.2 Cost structure

Table 9. Cost for minimal operations of the Science Mesh.

	FTE	Estimated Annual Cost (EUR)
Personnel		
Steering Group	0.25	17,500
Executive board	0.10	7,000
DevOps	0.5	35,000
Software maintenance	0.2	14,000
Helpdesk	0.5	35,000
Others		
Miscellaneous costs (e.g., web domain, central services)		5,000
Total costs		78,500

While the Science Mesh is operating with minimal costs, the team needs to seek additional investments to maximize the impact the Science Mesh has to users. These additional investments are discussed in Section 5 on the Strategic Roadmap for the Science Mesh.

4.3 Funding model

Herein we explore various revenue streams which could be used to secure sustainability for the Science Mesh. While grant funding is likely to continue playing an important role in the future deployment of the Science Mesh; to become self-sustainable over time, it will need to generate its own revenue. We explore various funding models including membership fees, service fees, and platform fees. In addition, we briefly elaborate on alternative sources of revenue, such as third-party vendor platform fees and leveraging industrial customers through consulting.

4.3.1 Grant funding

As a public good that aims to serve the wider research community, government funding is the most natural choice for financing the operations of an initiative as ambitious as the Science Mesh, particularly during its initial years and as it attracts its first users. Indeed, at the time of writing, the CS3MESH4EOSC Project has received a total EU contribution of € 5 858 571,25 under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement no. 863353).

Grant funding remains the status quo, at least initially, also for other similar initiatives. This is demonstrated by a recent report¹⁴ written by the EOSC Financial Sustainability Task Force.

¹⁴ <https://www.eosc.eu/sites/default/files/2022-11/financial-sustainability-tf-progress-report-nov-2022.pdf>

The report explored the funding models of four data federations, namely [Blue-Cloud](#), [CESSDA ERIC](#), [DiSSCO](#), and the [COVID-19 data platform](#). Indeed, for all four uses cases, the costs of data resources, operations, and maintenance costs were mainly financed by European Commission and/or member state grants.

The initial CS3MESH4EOSC grant funding has been instrumental in securing the future of the platform; with it, we expect to have created the conditions so that the Science Mesh starts providing concrete demonstrations of its benefits to early users. Future cost-benefit analyses will have to be conducted, to be able to convince funders and policymakers of the value of this new ecosystem. Such analyses should be undertaken once there is sufficient user uptake (i.e., the service is fully operating in production, with all its main applications available to its users), or it risks being inaccurate and incomprehensive. A sufficient user base will allow critical data to be collected (e.g., aspects which are most useful and what needs improvement) that will allow for much better precision in the results.

4.3.2 Membership fees for research institutions or EFSS nodes

The first alternative revenue stream to explore is that of membership fees charged to either research institutions or EFSS services that have joined the Science Mesh. Although this represents an interesting revenue model, the difficulty lies in proving that the Science Mesh generates sufficient value to justify the fees.

Nevertheless, there are some examples of similar projects that have explored this scenario, such project being the EUDAT Collaborative Data Infrastructure, an infrastructure enabling integrated data services and resources for research through its network of more than 25 research organisations, data, and computing centres. According to EUDAT reports¹⁵, member institutions pay an annual membership fee of € 5,000 – € 20,000 depending on their level of engagement.

Another EU-funded project, TRIPLE (Transforming Research through Innovative Practices for Linked interdisciplinary Exploration), is a discovery platform for social sciences and humanities which also suggested¹⁶ a membership pricing model. The model is based on two membership types – Sustaining Memberships and Visionary Memberships. Sustaining Memberships range from € 500 – 3000 annually, depending on the relevant country income class (i.e., Lower & middle-income countries: € 500; High-income countries/small organisations: € 1,500; High-income countries/large organisations: € 3,000); while Visionary Memberships range from € 900 – 6000 annually, also depending on the relevant country

¹⁵ D2.10: EUDAT2020 Business Plan, Rob Baxter, <http://www.eudat.eu/>

¹⁶ Breitfuss, Gert, Disch, Leonie, Holsinger, Sy, Provost, Lottie, Di Donato, Francesca, & Dumouchel, Suzanne. (2023). TRIPLE Deliverable 7.4: Final Report on Exploitation and Sustainability Strategy (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708878>

income class (i.e., Lower & middle-income countries: € 900; High-income countries/small organisations: € 3,000; High-income countries/large organisations: € 6,000).

Data from these two similar projects may serve as points of reference moving forward.

4.3.2.1 Research Institutions

The proposal here is simple but has significant scope for modification and diversification of options: research institutions who want to provide access to the Science Mesh for researchers within their organization are charged an annual membership fee. Crucially, here in the individual researcher incurs zero costs (Figure 4).

Figure 4. This schematic diagram illustrates the researcher's institution paying a service provider (in this case, the Science Mesh, not an EFSS service) to provide an individual researcher with free access to the Science Mesh. Figure taken from *Towards Sustainable Funding Models for the European Open Science Cloud, Financial Sustainability Task Force Progress report, November 2022*.

We believe that a Tiered Pricing Model may be particularly appealing to research institutions. Essentially, a tiered pricing strategy will offer the Science Mesh services to users (i.e., research institutions) at different price points based on the level of features, functionality, or usage in that respective tier. For example, given the architecture of the Science Mesh offering, all tiers will need to include the 'Federated Layer Service' as this is the interoperability layer that allows different EFSS nodes to communicate with another. Tiers will then have varying price points and will contain combinations of different Science Mesh Data Services (i.e., Data Science Environments, Open Data Systems, On-demand data transfers, and Collaborative documents). There is tremendous scope for modification of this model; for example, additional Science Mesh technical components, beyond simply the data services, can be added into the tiered pricing model. Moreover, the model can be specifically adjusted to accommodate for the essential operations costs. For example, certain low-resource plans may be made available freely, with revenue provided by high-resource plans sustaining the Science Mesh operations.

Overall, tiered pricing will offer various advantages to research institutions, including cost savings (i.e., they can choose plans that fit their specific research needs and budget), flexibility (i.e., they can scale their plans up or down), and accessibility (i.e., including low price points allows affordable entry points for smaller organizations).

A fictional example use-case of this model in action: a Dutch research institution uses SURF Drive, an EFSS service that has already joined the Science Mesh, for its cloud computing needs. However, the specific research agenda and circumstances at this research institution means that researchers are not interested in all the Science Mesh data services. Instead, they are only interested in sharing data between their institution and collaborators, that use CERNBox – a different EFSS service that is also part of the Science Mesh. As such, the research institution in question can pay membership fees for a plan that includes only (a) access to the Science Mesh federated layer and (b) the On-demand data transfers service.

4.3.2.2 EFSS services

Further upstream from research institutions are individual EFSS services (or sites) which the research institutions utilize, often provided by governmental entities, such as NRENs, or research clusters. The EFSS services that may decide to join the Science Mesh network will be well-established, financially resilient, and typically have a large userbase. As such, it is reasonable to consider a scenario whereby they will be required to pay a membership fee for joining the Science Mesh.

The most apparent challenge for this proposal is identifying the best incentive for EFSS services to pay membership fees. Essentially, does the Science Mesh produce enough value for the EFSS service to offset the costs of joining? Answering this is certainly not simple. However, that being said, there are some EFSS services with a transparent academic agenda that have been geared toward Open Science from their inception. SURFdrive, for example, an EFSS node of the Science Mesh, is a personal cloud service designed for the Dutch education and research system. This service embraces the concept of Open Science and is constantly developing new IT solutions for research. Similar offers are provided by PSNC in Poland, SWITCH in Switzerland and CESNET in Czechia. EFSS services operating within this domain certainly represent a possible customer base that might be willing to pay membership fees to join the Science Mesh.

4.3.3 Service fees for researchers

For the sake of thoroughness, we've included in this exercise the unappealing option of charging Science Mesh service fees from individual researchers.

Having researchers pay for using the Science Mesh is a highly inadvisable strategy for several reasons: researchers, especially those from small institutions, may not have the

financial capacity to pay for the service – creating a barrier to entry and limiting the pool of researchers using the service. Naturally, this will negatively impact the overall impact of the Science Mesh and the collaboration it is promoting. Charging individual researchers will also lead to general billing complications and administration; not only will there be a greater volume of individual transactions to handle, but many researchers will need to channel their purchase through their institution – a process which can be time-consuming.

Moreover, and perhaps more importantly, the CS3MESH4EOSC Project strives to combine various disjointed and fragmented cloud services to boost open-science by generating a joint, coordinated service to users in the research and education space at a pan-European level. This objective is fundamental to the Project’s vision, and implementing service fees for individual researchers will more than likely jeopardize this.

4.3.4 Third-party vendor platform fees

An additional potential source of revenue is charging third-party vendor fees. Third-party vendors may offer products or services that integrate within the Science Mesh architecture (i.e., software applications, security, storage, etc.). It is important, however, that third-party vendors are evaluated and selected via a rigid set of criteria – ensuring they are secure, reliable, provide a product/service that is compatible with the Science Mesh, and importantly, are a product/service that the end-users will value.

There are not many disadvantages of including this model as a revenue stream; the potential revenue provided by third-party vendors may not be insignificant, and charging fees can help ensure that only high-quality vendors are attracted to the Science Mesh. That being said, the two primary challenges of this model are firstly, convincing third-party vendors that the platform is viable, and secondly, having the vendors produce content which end-users will value.

4.3.5 Subsidization from commercial users and activities

A promising potential stream of revenue is found in leveraging the financial capacity of industry users. More specifically, we highlight here three business model options presented¹⁷ by the Photon and Neutron Open Science Cloud (PaNOSC) Project: (1) Complete environment for data search, analysis, simulation, and storage (a key point here being that industry will not work with their own data, only existing open data); (2) Improving company’s staff skills on data analysis and access to related tools; (3) Complete consultancy service. These three models are fascinating, and their utility will be simple, leverage these industry-specific

¹⁷ D7.3 Paan EOSC Business model reference document, Angela Zennaro, Giuseppe La Rocca, Ornela de Giacomo and Teodor Ivanoaica, Available at: <https://github.com/panosc-eu>

opportunities to finance the core Science Mesh services provided to the research environment.

PaNOSC unpacks each model further; revenue can be extracted from model 2 by receiving cash payments after giving access to training courses. Thereafter, freemium access (discussed in Section 4.3.6) can be allocated to software for post-training data analysis. Alternatively, cash payments are received after giving access to software/computing tools, followed by free training courses. Similarly, a complete consultancy service can generate large amounts of revenue in return for providing a wide range of consulting services.

Similarly, the FAIR4Health Project¹⁸ placed one of its KERs, namely a Data Curation Tool, at the centre of its business model. The Data Curation Tool is a tool that caters to the needs of health-related organizations aiming to transform their health data into FAIR data. The target market for this tool would include healthcare facilities such as health institutions, health research centres, regional governments, and ministries of health that hold healthcare data. The revenue model for this Tool is briefly; (1) a free version including direct use of open-source version; and (2) a premium version which includes four services, namely training, consulting and support, assistance (i.e., using Tool on behalf of customer), and an adjustment service for adding new customer-specific functionalities.

While the pathways by which the Science Mesh can leverage industry are not yet known, it is certainly clear that accessing the financial resources of industrial customers offers some appeal.

4.3.6 Additional Pricing Strategies

There are several pricing strategies that may be employed at any of the Science Mesh customer segments (e.g., the previously mentioned Tiered Pricing Strategy), each of which has different trade-offs. These pricing strategies were gathered after assessing the OpenAIRE sustainability report¹⁹.

1. **Per user pricing:** This strategy charges customers based on the number of registered accounts. Despite being one of the simplest pricing models, the costs can add up quickly (especially for large research groups) and may well discourage the adoption of Open Science.

¹⁸ D6.3 Business model & marketing strategy for products/services derived from FAIR data reuse in health domains, Mert Gencturk, www.fair4health.eu

¹⁹ D2.3, OpenAIRE - CONNECTing scientific results in support of Open Science, Sustainability Report, N. Manola, www.openaire.eu

2. **Per active user pricing:** This strategy charges customers based on the number of active users on the platform. This model may be more amenable to research communities as they'll only pay for users that are actively using the service.
3. **Freemium model:** This strategy offers a free basic service and charges users for additional features. This model may well encourage the adoption of the Science Mesh, by providing an entry-level service at no cost, but it may also deter users from paying if they believe the entry-level service meets their needs.
4. **Pay-as-you-go pricing:** This strategy charges users based on the specific resources they use. While this offers great flexibility for users, it can make it challenging for the Science Mesh to forecast its revenue and the research community to predict its costs.
5. **Per feature pricing:** This strategy charges users based on the features they use, regardless of how much they use them. It can be an appealing strategy to the research community as it offers a clear pricing structure, allowing researchers to pay for exactly what they need, instead of often-inconvenient packages. The large challenge herein lies in defining price points for each feature. As a closing note, the current state of the Science Mesh dictates that grant funding is likely the most viable solution for the immediate continuation of the Project. To ensure then that this funding is acquired, demonstrating the real-world application of the Science Mesh will be crucial; highlighting that is not just a theoretical concept with a great value proposition on paper. Growing then an active user base will be critical to achieve for the Science Mesh.

Beyond grant funding, however, the Science Mesh will need to become self-sustainable over time by generating its own revenue. Of course, this would make the Project far less reliant on external funding sources (e.g., grants) and will allow greater flexibility and control over its operations. In lieu of this, we explore several potential revenue streams that could help the Project become self-sustainable over time. These alternate revenue models include membership fees, service fees, and platform fees. However, it is essential to recognize that these options may not be viable in these early stages of the Project. In all these discussions, it is important to emphasize that the exploration of revenue models is compounded by the predicament of charging a fee to Science Mesh users (whether this be researchers, research organizations, or EFSS nodes) all the while advocating Open Science.

5 Strategic Roadmap

Given all the previous discussions on the challenges and opportunities with respect to the Science Mesh, we discuss the next steps for its implementation (Figure 55). Towards achieving sustainability, we see 4 areas that the Science Mesh needs to invest on that we can organize into two axes. First, these actions can either be directed internally to improve the technical implementation of the Science Mesh or externally to bolster the impact of the Science Mesh to key stakeholders. Second, these actions can either be directed towards the service providers/research infrastructures (macro) or the users/scientific communities (micro).

Figure 5. Framework to understand the sustainability directions of the Science Mesh.

After the funding ends, it would be crucial to maintain the essential operations of the Science Mesh. As mentioned in Section 4.1, this includes the steering committee, the executive board, software maintenance, DevOps and service desk. While funding these essential operations would enable the Science Mesh to continue operating at a minimum level, further investments are needed for the Science Mesh to achieve its maximum potential and achieve a state where it can generate revenues to sustain itself without relying further on external grants.

Investments should be made to enrol new nodes to the Science Mesh. It is important that the Science Mesh is constantly expanding and integrating new cloud services to enable interoperability across them. It is crucial that connecting to the Science Mesh is done on through an intuitive and frictionless enrolment process. To encourage more providers to join the Science Mesh, it is essential to highlight the benefits of participation. Tight integration with the larger EOSC initiative is also key to success. Analyses on various barriers challenging

them from connecting to the Science Mesh should be conducted to address these issues as soon as possible.

Second, on the technical side, it is important to empower service providers within the Science Mesh to be able to manage their respective nodes. More tools can be developed by the Science Mesh to extend or improve these technical capabilities such as to monitor their performance, manage access controls, and troubleshoot technical issues. User-friendly dashboards, for instance, can enable admins to see various emerging issues and more importantly, let them see the real impacts of the Science Mesh. The partners of the Science Mesh should also ensure their strong relationship with cloud software vendors like NextCloud and OwnCloud, and beyond, to ensure that the Science Mesh operates seamlessly with their systems.

Third, it would be crucial to engage with user communities. Even when there are many nodes connected to the Science Mesh, this will be futile unless the researchers under them know about the platform and use it. As such, it is important to engage with the user communities to constantly get their feedback, collect their use cases and analyse the impact of the platform. To maximize its use, it would be important to develop and provide training materials that demonstrate the various ways that the Science Mesh can augment their research workflows. User metrics should be closely tracked to ensure that the mesh ecosystem is hitting its goals.

Finally, new capabilities should be developed to keep up with the constant advances in data science and machine learning. While the first incarnation of the Science Mesh already comes with novel applications such as data science, environments, open data systems, on-demand data transfers and collaborative documents; new tools are always being developed and it would be important that some of those get integrated into the platform, and benefit from its interoperability functionality. In the long-term, the Science Mesh could provide a platform to enable software developers to have wider reach, possibly world-wide.

Putting these altogether, the strategic roadmap for the next decade is shown in the following table. We took inspiration in generating this roadmap from the Blue Cloud project, an Open Science platform for marine research²⁰.

²⁰ Vera, Julia, Larkin, Kate, Delaney, Conor, Tonné, Nathalie, Cisternino, Stefano, Calewaert, Jan-Bart, Pittonet Gaiarin, Sara, Drago, Federico, Schaap, Dick, Pagano, Pasquale, Cabrera, Patricia, Drudi, Massimiliano, Ellenbroek, Anton, & Obaton, Dominique. (2022, November 29). Blue-Cloud Strategic Roadmap - Executive summary (supporting material for Final Conference). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7377985>

Table 10. Strategic roadmap for the Science Mesh.

	Immediate needs <1 year	Medium term 3-5 years	Long term >5 years
Theme	Bridge	Grow	Sustain
Priority	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Exploring funding / sustainability pathways - Getting early adopter user communities to demonstrate the benefit of the Science Mesh - Enrol and deploy to all partner nodes - Publish early user stories 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish strategic partnerships with funding agencies to secure funding - Founding of official governing body - Enrol more nodes - Engage with more scientific communities - Improve the value of the product value for our customer to increase usage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become one of the main platforms which enable FAIR data and Open Science for researchers Europe-wide - Serve data privacy and data sovereignty - Enable collaborative research towards solving the increasingly complex problems facing society - Kickstart the movement towards interoperability across cloud providers
Internal roadmap for the Science Mesh			
Legal entity	Secure commitment from different parties (through an MoU or similar agreement)	Incorporation of Science Mesh organization	
Funding	Explore funding opportunities and write grants	Use secured funding to transition to self-sustainability	Implement self-sustainable revenue models
Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ongoing maintenance of the software to respond to bugs and various issues - Using, promoting, and contributing to developing APIs for server-to-server file-sharing, applications, and file-service interoperability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of new capabilities to empower administrators and better integration with cloud providers - Creating services/functionality for seamless user selection and group creation across sites/services - Creating services/functionality for metadata and seamless data publishing, searching and archiving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Enable third party software developers to augment and add value to the Science Mesh

Cloud providers supported	OwnCloud, NextCloud, and SeaFile	Ongoing support from these top academic cloud providers	Expansion to other cloud providers
External roadmap for the Science Mesh			
EOSC	Explore options for integration with EOSC	More streamlined integration with EOSC	Become one of the foundations enabling EOSC
Nodes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that intake procedure for new nodes is straightforward and frictionless - Implementing and deploying APIs at core sites in the form of site services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grow nodes - Engage with additional service providers and extending ScienceMesh into a pan-European service, reaching users across the continent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain network of nodes - Showcase impact to data sovereignty and interoperability
Users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Ensure that users can conveniently take advantage of the Science Mesh through a training program - Engage with research communities and create data-centric applications for selected scientific use cases. - Publish user stories of success - Closely track user feedback 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Grow users - Constantly track and improve user engagement - Impact analysis of user 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintain network of users - Showcase impact on users - Highlight impact on finding, accessing, interoperation and reuse of data
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Engage with industry players to understand value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate industry players to the Science Mesh 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Let industry play an active role in developing and extending the Science Mesh
Roadmap for the Services within the Mesh			
Data Science Environments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Find specific use cases to demonstrate benefit of such environment - Launch the initial version - Receive feedback from early adopters and iterate on the product - Explore funding opportunities for further development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Add more users and retain existing ones - Add more advanced features such as version control, automated testing, and debugging tools - Partner with industry to promote adoption and usage of the environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become primary collaborative data science environment used by researchers - Build a community around the environment to foster collaboration and knowledge sharing
Open Data Systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch the initial version of the system with basic features and capabilities - Build partnerships with research communities to demonstrate benefit 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promote system's compliance with data privacy regulations and standards - Expand functionalities such as data quality assurance tools and processes to ensure data accuracy and consistency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Become de facto workflow for FAIR data - Establish the system as a go-to source for open research data

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Conduct user experience and workflow observations of researchers - Funding needed to maintain and widen adoption 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Integrate with other systems and platforms to make data more accessible and useful 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Foster a community of data providers, users, and contributors to promote collaboration and knowledge sharing
On-demand data transfers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch the initial version of the transfer system with basic features and capabilities - Highlight use case and benefits in convenience 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expand the range of supported data transfer protocols - Integrate with other systems and platforms to facilitate further data transfers across different environments - Develop data encryption and security features to protect data during transfers 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish the transfer system as a reliable and efficient way to move data across different environments - Continuously improve the system's infrastructure to support scalability, availability, and security
Collaborative documents	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Launch initial version - Demonstrate utility with early adopter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expand the range of supported document formats and editors - Develop tools and features to facilitate collaboration, version control and citation management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Establish the document collaboration system as a go-to platform for collaborative research writing

6 Risk assessment

The risk assessment presented here was developed in the context of the Horizon Results Booster PDES-C service²¹ delivered to the CS3MESH4EOSC Project and the main outcomes of the exploitation strategy seminar held on the 7th and 8th of February 2022.

The risk assessment comprises two elements; firstly, a risk matrix which aids in identifying the types of risk, the relative level of importance, the probability of risks occurring, as well as remedy actions and their probability to succeed (Table 11).

The risk matrix analyses include six different categories of risks:

1. **Partnership Risks** – internal risk factors related to the composition of the partnership or specific behaviours of the partners, conflict of interests, etc.
2. **Technological Risks** – external factors related to the feasibility of the technology, its level of development, presence of other emerging technologies, etc.
3. **Market Risks** – external risk factors related to fulfilment of marked needs, presence of competitors or alternative products, etc.
4. **IPR Risks** – factors related to the presence of similar previous patents, the possibility to protect the developed technology/product, patent counterfeit, etc.
5. **Environmental risks** – external factors related to the presence or changing in legislations, standards, etc.
6. **Financial risks** – factors related to the availability of funds for bringing the research stage to prototyping industrialisation/commercialisation.

The risk severity (i.e., the importance of the risk with respect to successful exploitation) multiplied by the risk probability results in a final risk grade of the concerned risk factor. A high-risk grade and a low probability of intervention success represents a severe scenario where project cessation should be considered (i.e., Warning). A high-risk grade coupled with a high probability of intervention success represents a scenario where immediate action is needed to ensure exploitation (i.e., Action). A low-risk grade coupled with a high probability of intervention success represents a situation where monitoring of the situation is required (i.e., Control). And finally, a low-risk grade and a low probability of intervention success represents a scenario that doesn't require immediate action (i.e., No action).

²¹ PDES – Module C Final Report for CS3MESH4EOSC. Interactive and agile/responsive sharing mesh of storage, data and applications for EOSC; Exploitation Strategy Seminar delivered on 7th and 8th of February 2022; Provided by: Tomasz Cichocki

Table 11. Risk assessment matrix for the Science Mesh. This table was adapted from the PDES – Module C Final Report for CS3MESH4EOOSC²².

Risk	Significance 1 – low 10 – high	Probability 1 – low 10 – high	Risk Grade	Potential intervention	Intervention Feasibility* 1 – low 10 – high	Classification
Partnership						
"Waterfall fallacy" that halts project execution and exploitation of the results (e.g., do not engage with the users before the results are available).	9	8	72	Engaging with potential users: interviews, questionnaires, social media, etc	7	ACTION
The industry/vendors don't find the project relevant and don't actively collaborate.	9	5	45	Reducing dependency on the vendors	7	CONTROL
Did not engage with Science Mesh end-users.	9	8	72	Engage with users, lobbying, signing up new people	7	ACTION
Did not engage with people who will maintain the infrastructure.	9	7	63	Identification and definition of governance structure	8	ACTION
Dependence on CERN or some entity to lead the Science Mesh.	5	5	25	Identification and definition of governance structure	8	CONTROL
Lack of core group of people who will sustain the infrastructure.	9	7	63	Development of future sustainability plan	8	ACTION
Technological						
Risk of higher maintenance costs than planned.	8	5	40	Cost and benefit analysis	8	CONTROL
The work which was done is not "good" enough to represent a viable alternative to other existing solutions.	9	6	54	Define product differentiation strategy	5	ACTION/ WARNING
Technology fails to substitute already existing solutions.						
Lack of clarity on what is demanded for FAIR.	8	2	16	Talking with potential stakeholders	8	CONTROL
Market						
A competitor in the market with a stronger UVP (perceived).	9	8	72	Increasing of marketing of the Science Mesh	9	ACTION

²² PDES – Module C Final Report for CS3MESH4EOOSC. Interactive and agile/responsive sharing mesh of storage, data and applications for EOOSC; Exploitation Strategy Seminar delivered on 7th and 8th of February 2022; Provided by: Tomasz Cichocki

Customer reception and acceptance of technology not as planned.	9	8	72	Collecting feedback from the universities/research organizations in the EU	9	ACTION
Market penetration slower than planned.	7	8	56	Increasing of marketing of the Science Mesh	9	ACTION
No one buys the product: problems addressed by the solutions are not the actual problems felt by the customers.	8	8	64	Talking with potential users (researchers)	9	ACTION
No one uses the Science Mesh: the communities which were invited to participate haven't kept using it.						
Very little feedback/interest on social media (Twitter) => we are not known beyond CS3 community => resulting in not enough uptake and interest.	9	9	81	Engage with users, lobbying, signing up new people	8	ACTION
BigTech Competitors come up with similar research-oriented solutions and the community sticks to them.	9	6	54	Communicating to users about data privacy issues linked to commercial solutions	9	ACTION
Society doesn't find need for Open Science/FAIR data.	7	2	14	Science Mesh can pivot to offer different capabilities to potential users	9	CONTROL
Legal						
Customer doesn't meet contractual requirements.	7	4	28	Familiarizing with different regulations/bureaucracy across diverse countries	9	CONTROL
Financial/Management						
Funding finished with no possibility of extension and a lot of unfinished work.						
Lack of funding leads to death of the project.	8	5	40	Applying for a public fund extension/private funding	8	CONTROL
Delay in securing the needed financing for further developing the solution.						
Inadequate definition of the business plan.	9	5	45	In-depth conversations with all the partners of the Science Mesh	9	CONTROL

Bureaucracy has made it impossible to establish new partnerships.	6	2	12	Familiarizing with different regulations/bureaucracy across diverse countries	8	CONTROL
Environmental/Regulatory/Safety						
Incentives/disincentives decided by others (e.g., political level).	8	9	72	Get in touch with the state/university/research representatives	9	ACTION
Legislative barriers related to data management, data protection.	7	4	28	Getting familiar with different regulations/bureaucracy across diverse countries/Get in touch with the state/university representatives	9	CONTROL
New legal framework/political decisions make it impossible to provide a useful platform.	8	2	16	Science Mesh can pivot to new possibilities withing new legal framework	8	CONTROL

7 Conclusion

In conclusion, the Science Mesh is poised to unleash collaborative research potential by providing a seamless data platform that will impact the research community, service providers, industry, and society. Specifically, it will enable data FAIRness, allow for new applications of data, and address issues related to data sovereignty and vendor lock-in. In addition, it will address the fragmentation and lack of interoperability across the cloud landscape.

To maximize the impact of the Science Mesh and ensure its sustainability, it is important to be transparent about its value and limitations, which were presented in the lean canvas Section 3. Section 4 and 5 outlined the strategic roadmap and risk mitigation measures needed for the long-term sustainability of the Science Mesh.

As emphasized in this report, at present, further investments are necessary to achieve sustainability, and securing the next phase of funding is critical to this end. This will allow for the enrolment of new nodes, the creation of value for node administrators, the enrolment of new users, and the enablement of new collaborative functionalities. By demonstrating its clear value, the Science Mesh can transition away from reliance on governmental grants and achieve self-sustainability.

Regarding its current technological status, the ScienceMesh remains a tool under development that is not yet open to the public. Considering this, the CS3MESH4EOSC consortium has focused on creating a community of *potential* users. Expressions of interest will be converted into Science Mesh adoption (i.e., as users, adopters, or contributors) as soon as it is open to the public (for more detail, refer to Deliverable 5.3 – “Final report on dissemination and exploitation of project results”).